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CREATION OF INNOVATIVE PROJECTS IN SMALL AND MEDIUM BUSINESS**Abuzyarova Zh.**

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Abstract

One of the priority areas for the development of the modern economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan today is a process aimed at developing and supporting small and medium-sized businesses. Creating innovative conditions in small and medium-sized businesses is a priority task, the solution of which depends not only on the formation of innovative processes, but also on the demand for technological innovations.

Keywords: innovation, small and medium business, information technology, innovation project

Introduction

Currently, one of the priority areas for the development of the economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan is the process aimed at developing and supporting small and medium-sized businesses. Applying practical measures to strengthen the scientific and technical potential and involve it in the real economic process, Kazakhstan, as well as in any developed or developing country, strives for enterprises to be financially stable and their products competitive. To this end, priority areas of scientific and technical activity have been identified, scientific research is being carried out to identify new cost-effective technologies and forms of doing business, and innovations are being actively introduced in production.

Innovation is an intellectual product that has entered the sphere of production, implemented in this area and led to its significant changes.

One of the priority tasks, the solution of which determines the formation of innovative processes, as well as the demand for technological innovations, is the creation of innovative conditions in the manufacturing sector. Under these conditions, enterprises should have the potential to accumulate funds for innovation. This is a common task for all aspects of economic policy and

one of the main measures to get the economy out of the crisis.

The fundamental task is the accumulation of human capital, knowledge, skills, skills of employees, ensuring the growth of labor productivity. The introduction and development of high-tech industries is provided by specialists of appropriate qualifications. The main conditions for the development of science and innovation in the industrial sector are the requirements for the quality and scope of education, especially higher education, the inclusion of research work in the educational process.

There is a need to use modern information technologies, programs for receiving, processing and sending information, network components, in particular such a global computer network as the Internet. При создании инновационных проектов в малом и среднем бизнесе необходима также законодательная база для защиты интеллектуальной собственности, а также по поддержки инновационных проектов.

The creation and implementation of innovation is designed to produce an effect. There are the following types of effect from innovations:

1. economic - indicators take into account in value terms all types of results and costs due to the implementation of innovations;

2. scientific and technical - novelty, simplicity, usefulness, aesthetics, compactness;

3. financial - the calculation of indicators is based on financial indicators;

4. resource - indicators reflect the impact of innovation on the volume of production and consumption of a particular type of resource;

5. social - indicators take into account the social results of the implementation of innovations;

6. environmental - noise, electromagnetic field, illumination, vibration. The indicators take into account the impact of innovations on the environment.

The importance of innovation for enterprises is extremely high. The need for constant innovation is caused by a reduction in the life cycle of goods, services and other products, which occurs as a result of increased competition, increasing the rate of consumer addiction to new products, improving mass communication systems, the rapid development of science and changing technologies. For successful development, the enterprise must explore the emergence of new needs and opportunities to meet them. Competitor research is also relevant.

A long, expensive and risky process is the development of an innovative project. Each of these projects, regardless of the complexity and amount of work, goes through certain stages in its development: from the stage when "there is no project yet", to the stage when "the project is no longer there". The stages through which the project goes are called phases. This process can be represented as a cycle consisting of the following phases: pre-investment and investment.

At all stages of the innovation cycle, such projects are characterized by high uncertainty; moreover, innovations that have successfully passed the stage of testing and introduction into production may not be accepted by the market, and their production should be stopped. A number of projects at the initial stage of development give encouraging results, but later, with an unclear or technical and technological perspective, they can be closed. Even the most successful projects are not immune from failures; at any moment of their life cycle, competitors may have more promising new products.

Organization and implementation of an innovative project includes the following stages: development of an innovative idea; study of innovative probabilities; preparation of contract and project documentation; construction and installation works; facility operation; monitoring of economic indicators.

It is also necessary to establish the effectiveness of an innovative project, calculate the expected economic indicators and subject the results to consideration.

If we follow the classical canons of the theory of market economy, according to which the activities of economic entities are based on freedom of choice, and the functions of the state are reduced to regulating the processes of interaction between economic entities, then the conclusion is that it is necessary to single out at least two types of criteria for the effectiveness of

their activities. Firstly, these are local criteria for the effectiveness of the activities of economic entities, which, within the framework of external restrictions, seek to obtain the greatest benefits in the long term. Secondly, it is a global criterion for the efficiency of the entire economic system, which should underlie the state policy aimed at ensuring the dynamic development of the entire society. Recognition of the presence of two groups of heterogeneous and conflicting criteria requires the development of various methods for evaluating the effectiveness of investment and innovation projects, which, in accordance with the accepted classification, can be called macro- and microeconomic.

To assess the overall economic efficiency of innovations, a system of such indicators is used as: integral effect; profitability index; rate of return; payback period.

The main indicators that are used to compare investment projects and choose the best of them are indicators of the integral effect, that is, economic at the level of the national economy and commercial at the level of an individual organization.

The value of commercial risk strongly depends on the effectiveness of the work of scientific and technical organizations in carrying out applied research and development work.

The main objective of this software package is to create a unified database of technologies and innovative projects, which includes:

1) improvement of the technology for collecting and processing information, which involves one-time input and multiple use;

2) providing the user with the most complete information on all available technologies and innovations;

3) increasing the efficiency and quality of information services.

The program must perform the following functions:

- creation and maintenance of a database of technologies and innovative projects;

- access to database records using a modern interface;

- ensuring the selection of information according to specified criteria.

General requirements for the software package:

- completeness of information for the formation of the database;

- reliability of information;

- ensuring the reliability of information storage;

- ensuring the selectivity of the information provided.

The task must ensure that the following basic requirements are met:

— it is necessary to find a way to connect the database to the user's browser so that the latter can view the information available in the database;

— it is necessary to create such a program interface that will be simple for the user, and the requirements for network and server equipment are minimal.

— the user must be able to search for data by the project code and select information according to specified criteria;

– the text of the program should consist of separate modules, ensure minimal costs in the further development of the system and its transfer to other server platforms.

Based on the objectives of the project, it is necessary that the database supports the "client-server" technology, it is assumed that the designed information system will distribute functions between at least the client and the server, i.e. part of the functions of the application program will be performed on the "client", and the other part on the "server".

Conclusion

Thus, this project includes the latest achievements in the field of computer technology. Their use enables the user to obtain the necessary data from the database located on the server as efficiently and quickly as possible.

Currently, a pilot version of the data bank of technologies and innovative projects has been developed. The use of the proposed software product provides:

- 1) the ability to use the application, both in local and global Internet networks;
- 2) limited access to the system (user rights - only viewing data; administrator rights - viewing and changing (editing) data);

3) viewing and changing the database (adding new innovative projects to the database, deleting projects, editing project data);

4) search for an innovative project by a given value, namely, by the code of an innovative project;

5) selection of a set of innovative projects according to specified criteria, namely, the selection of projects is carried out according to specified criteria values such as payback period, investment volume, sales volume.

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MODERN APPROACHES TO THE ORGANIZATION OF QUALITY INCREASE IN THE BEAUTY AND COMMERCIAL MEDICINE INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This article reveals the problems of improving the activities of beauty industry companies. The article examines the strengths and opportunities that make up the strategic potential of a companies in beauty and commercial industry sector.

Keywords: beauty industry, innovative methods, process innovation, salon business

The beauty industry for the Kazakhstan market of services is quite a young direction. The current socio-economic situation and widespread socio-cultural values in the country significantly contribute to the development of the beauty services market. An organization that has entered this market should regularly carry out industry and strategic analysis of the external environment, since growing markets are always attractive for new business entities.

It is often difficult for the client to justify their dissatisfaction, and it is economically unprofitable for the master to recognize the defects of the service, so there are significantly fewer complaints in the documentation of the beauty industry company than upset visitors. The lack of customer feedback makes it difficult for enterprises to manage the quality of services provided and "disables" the competition mechanism. There are many companies in the beauty industry, and the consumer has to look for " their " master, who provides a high-quality service, for years, demonstrating their unsuccessful experience in the

most prominent place (Ennis & Harrington, 1999). Competition is a complex process, and companies must prove their leadership in the field of beauty almost daily, constantly working on the level of their service and the quality of services provided.

The beauty studio as an object of promotion in the market is a very specific structure. Salon business is a complex type of service, because it involves a lot of qualified specialists, including those from the medical field. Due to the fact that the salon business market is currently on the rise, the services they provide are extremely popular. The beauty industry is a complex, highly competitive business, so an employee working with clients must be not only beautiful, but also smart, have strong communication skills, as well as managerial abilities that allow you to effectively organize the work of many specialists, manage customer records, and resolve possible conflict situations (Chen & Popovich, 2003).

The analysis of modern problems and trends in the activities of organizations, as well as the peculiarities